

SCHOOL ENVIRONMENT AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT OF STANDARD IX STUDENTS

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Abstract

The present study School Environment and Academic Achievement of standard IX students was probed to find the relationship between School Environment and Academic Achievement of standard IX students. Data for the study were collected using self-made School Environment Scale (SES). The investigator used stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample. The sample consists of 400 standard IX students. For analyzing data 't' test and Pearson's product moment co-efficient were the statistical techniques used. Finding shows there was no significant relationship between School Environment and Academic Achievement of standard IX students.

Key Words: School Environment, Academic Achievement, standard IX students.

INTRODUCTION

According to Dewey (1926) 'Education is a continuous process of experiencing and of revising or non-revising experiences It is the development of all those capacities in the individual, which enables him to control his environment and fulfill his possibilities' (Y.K.Singh, p.22). The forces of environment begin to influence the growth and development of the individual right from the womb of the mother. Educational process of development occurs in physical, social, cultural and psychological environment. A proper and adequate environment is very much necessary for a fruitful learning of the child. Especially the home and the school should provide the necessary stimulus for learning experience. The child spends most of his time in school and here his environment is exerting a different influence on performance through curricula, teaching techniques, relationship.

Jawaharlal Nehru declared that if all were well with our educational institutions, all would be well with the nation. Educational institutions are intimately linked with society at large. They are the temples of knowledge. They are the agents of social change and transformation. Therefore, the general condition of our schools, colleges and universities is a matter of great concern to the nation. Environment plays a vital role in the development of the personality of the students. As a student spends most of his life at school, the school environment is highly responsible for the inculcating of great values in him. The Kothari Commission (1964-66) has beautifully said, "The destiny of India is now being shaped in her classrooms" (p.2). As students are the backbones of the nation it is important to maintain a healthy school environment.

SIGNIFICANCE OF THE STUDY

In this ever-growing competitive world everyone desires a high level of achievement as the mark of one's performance. The whole system of education is centered on academic achievement of students, making it a fertile ground for research work. Learning takes places effectively only when proper and congenial environment is provided for children in classroom. Their learning environment plays an inherent role in moulding the innate potentialities of the individual and school has always been regarded as an important factor

in the child's education. The education of the child and his achievement is determined to a large extent by the varied and dynamic role of teachers and the facilities provided by them for the child's education. Since the environment influences on the academic achievement of the students, the investigator tries to find out the impact of school environment factors on achievement. Hence the investigator selected the topic.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Statement of the problem is entitled as "School Environment and Academic Achievement of standard IX students". The investigator adopted the following definitions for the terms used in this title.

School Environment

According to Mick Zais (2011), School Environment means the extent to which school settings promote student safety and student health, which may include topics such as the physical plant, the academic environment, available physical and mental health supports and services, and the fairness and adequacy of disciplinary procedures, as supported by relevant research and an assessment of validity.

Academic Achievement

A measure of knowledge gained in formal education usually indicated by test scores, grade, grade points, average and degrees. Here, the achievement level of the student is judged by the marks that the students have scored in the quarterly examinations.

Standard IX Students

The education given in the school at 9th Standard.

Objective

To find the relationship between School Environment and Academic Achievement of standard IX students.

Null Hypotheses

1. There is no significant difference between standard IX boys and girls in their school environment.
2. There is no significant difference between standard IX English and Tamil medium students in their school environment.
3. There is no significant difference between standard IX rural and urban school students in their school environment.
4. There is no significant difference between standard IX boys and girls in their academic achievement.
5. There is no significant difference between standard IX English and Tamil medium students in their academic achievement.
6. There is no significant difference between standard IX rural and urban school students in their academic achievement.
7. There is no significant relationship between the school environment and academic achievement of standard IX students.

METHOD

School Environment Scale was developed by the investigators were used for the collection of data. Item validity was found by the investigator in item-whole correlation method and reliability of the tools was found through test-retest method. The reliability of School Environment Scale was 0.74. The investigator has adopted survey method for this study. For academic achievement the investigator collected the quarterly marks of the students from their class teachers.

Population for this study was students studying IX standard in high and higher secondary schools in Tirunelveli district.

The investigator used stratified random sampling technique for selecting the sample. The sample consists of 400 students studying IX standard.

For analyzing data 't' test and Pearson's product moment correlation were used as the statistical techniques.

Data Analysis And Findings

Findings based on the hypotheses and followed by data analysis are given as follows;

Table 1: Difference In The School Environment Of Standard IX Boys & Girls

School Environment	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark at 5% level of significance
	Boys	191	119.20	11.80	0.70	1.96	Not Significant
	Girls	209	118.36	12.35			

Table 1 shows that there is no significant difference between standard IX boys and girls in their school environment.

Table 2: Difference In The School Environment Of Standard IX English & Tamil Medium Students

School Environment	Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark at 5% level of significance
	English	60	116.62	15.02	1.24	1.96	Not Significant
	Tamil	340	119.14	11.47			

Table 2 shows that there is no significant difference between standard IX English and Tamil medium students in their school environment.

Table 3: Difference In The School Environment Of Standard IX Rural & Urban Students

School Environment	Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark at 5% level of significance
	Rural	310	118.13	12.82	2.39	1.96	Significant
	Urban	90	120.94	8.83			

Table 3 shows that there is significant difference between standard IX rural and urban school students in their school environment.

Table 4: Difference In The Academic Achievement Of Standard IX Boys & Girls

Academic Achievement	Gender	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark at 5% level of significance
	Boys	191	265.71	88.37	0.02	1.96	Not Significant
	Girls	209	265.87	84.87			

Table 4 shows that there is no significant difference between standard IX boys and girls in their academic achievement.

Table 5: Difference In The Academic Achievement Of Standard IX English & Tamil Medium Students

Academic Achievement	Medium of Instruction	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark at 5% level of significance
	English	60	348.78	66.36	10.14	1.96	Significant
	Tamil	340	251.15	81.21			

Table 5 shows that there is significant difference between standard IX English and Tamil medium students in their academic achievement.

Table 6: Difference In The Academic Achievement Of Standard IX Rural & Urban Students

Academic Achievement	Locality of School	N	Mean	SD	Calculated 't' Value	Table Value	Remark at 5% level of significance
	Rural	310	270.85	86.74	2.23	1.96	Significant
	Urban	90	248.36	83.57			

Table 6 shows that there is significant difference between standard IX rural and urban school students in their academic achievement.

Table 7: Relationship Between School Environment And Academic Achievement Of Standard IX Students

School Environment and Academic Achievement	N	Calculated γ Value	Table Value	Remark at 5% level of significance
	400	0.024	0.098	NS

Table 7 shows that there is no significant relationship between the school environment and academic achievement of standard IX students.

CONCLUSION

Based on the analysis of data the investigators conclude the finding that there is no significant difference in the school environment of standard IX students in terms of gender, medium of instruction. At the same time, there is significant difference in the school environment of standard IX students in terms of locality of school. The urban students have better school environment than the rural students. This is due to the fact that urban students are having very much stressful environment in their day-to-day life because they are living in the mechanical and hurry burry life. So, they feel school environment is very convenient for their studies.

There is no significant difference in the academic achievement of standard IX students in terms of gender. But, there is significant difference in the academic achievement of standard IX students in terms of medium of instruction and locality of school.

There is no significant relationship between the school environment and academic achievement of standard IX students.

From the present study it is found that the school environment of standard IX students is low. It is found out that there is very low positive relationship between the school environment and academic achievement. To make the achievement to a high level, efforts must be taken to strengthen the school environment. So that, the

environment boosts up not only the achievement of students but their social ability, healthy status and moral values also.

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